

IMPROVING ASSESSMENT OF B2 LEVEL ENGLISH LEARNERS' WRITING COMPETENCE USING GOOGLE CLASSROOM PLATFORM

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses how to improve assessment of B2 level learners' writing competence using Google classroom platform. Author of this research investigated and reviewed a number of local and international scientists' and methodologists' researches and books and cited them accordingly. At the same time, some possible ways of assessing writing skill of B2 level learners were illustrated in the result and discussion part. Findings and results of this article can be used by other researchers for the future development of this issue.

1.1. Introduction. Learning, specifically, language learning highly depends on the assessment for the reason that it motivates the learner and enhance the process. As technology develops, traditional ways of assessment are becoming less productive. The need for the innovative forms of evaluation urges researchers and methodologists to investigate alternative options for teaching. There are a number of online and offline modern techniques to assess language aspects and skills as well as writing.

Writing is productive skill that require special attention from both the writer and the assessor. Using traditional means like paper and pen wastes time and effort. In this article researcher tried to use Google classroom platform to upload some tasks for the students for writing.

1.2. Literature review. Nearly everyone in the world use Google for many purposes, but do we ever consider the efficiency of this platform on language learning process? Here in the site Tech&Learning the definition of the Google Classroom is given: 'Google Classroom is a suite of online tools that allows teachers to set assignments, have work submitted by students, to mark, and to return graded papers. It was created as a way to get eliminate paper in classes and to make digital learning possible. It was initially planned for use with laptops in schools, such as Chromebooks, in order to allow the teacher and students to more efficiently share information and assignments'(Luke Edwards, 2022). Since Google Classroom is online-based, you can access it in some form from pretty much any device with a web browser. Processing is done at Google's end mostly, so even older devices are able to handle most of Google's resources.

But the issue is how to use Google Classroom to assess writing skill of the language learners. It is often assumed that the best way to test writing ability is to get the learners to write. That may seem obvious but, particularly at lower levels, being asked to write a whole, properly staged and formed text from scratch is a daunting and challenging task which may demotivate and depress our learners. The other issue is that reliably evaluating our learners' ability with a malformed, disorganized and inaccurately written text as the only data source is almost impossible.

In language teaching, four skills must be taught: listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Of the four skills, writing is the most complex skill (Durga & Rao, 2018). Writing is essential to be taught since writing allows students to think creatively and improve their vocabularies (Dewi, 2020). Writing certainly also requires assessment to evaluate student writing which will later be used as a reference for reflection to improve students' writing abilities (Dolin & Evans, 2018). Therefore, assessment for writing still should be done even in online learning. A study conducted by Yusuf (2019) indicates that the application of assessment, especially in the form of feedbacks, supported the students in developing their writing skills. An effective online assessment should have various kinds of assessment with clear explanation, the provision of feedback, clear assessment rubrics, and interaction between teachers and students on the online platform so that there are no misunderstandings about the assignment given (Gaytan & McEwen, 2007). A study conducted by Vonderwell, Liang, & Alderman (2007) suggested that the teachers need to have a deeper understanding of the terms of assessment for learning and learning assessment. Meanwhile, Google classroom is one of the most convenient platform to comment and give feedback by both the peers and the mentor. This all allows teachers and students to use Google Classroom since they can connect with it via any personal device.

1.3. Methodology. The researcher used experimental method in order to gather data on how to assess learners' writing skills using Google classroom platform. This study was a qualitative study which used narrative inquiry, where the data were collected through interviews with a research subject that can answer the research purpose (Josselson, 2011). The research subject was an English learners in 11th grade in a school in Tashkent, Mirzo Ulug'bek district. The pupils were chosen as the research subject in the present study because they had two years of experience in learning English during the Covid pandemic; they mostly submitted their writing assignment using messenger like Telegram and experienced online learning during the Covid-19 Pandemic. During the interview, pupils were asked their feedback on online assignments using messengers, most of them said it was time-consuming and boring. Nearly always, teacher had problem with assessing and giving feedback. But after using Google classroom each of the learners received grades and feedback from the educator

1.4. Conclusion. To sum up, research was successful. Implementing online assessment tools and learning platforms are efficient way of achieving intended result. Related to these findings, the present study implied that training on conducting assessment in writing, especially on online learning, is needed by the teachers to improve the implementation of online learning. Besides, since this research was still limited to the assessment of writing, it is recommended for other researchers to conduct other studies online assessments for other three skills: listening, speaking, and reading.

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